

The Condensations of Chloroform, Carbon-tetrachloride and Iodoform with Resorcinol and similar other Hydroxy Aromatic Compounds.

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Chloroform and carbontetrachloride have been previously employed in the synthesis of triphenylmethane and some of its derivatives. (Friedel and Craft, *Compt. rend.* 1877, 84, 1453; O. Fisher, *Annalen* 1879, 194, 254; Gomberg, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 3144; Haumann D.R.P. 68976; *Frdl.* III. 103; *Ann. Chim. Phys.* VI. 1, 489.) In all these cases Friedel and Crafts' method or a modification of it was employed, $AlCl_3$ or $ZnCl_2$ being used as a condensing agent. In the year 1858 Hofmann observed that aniline when heated with carbontetrachloride yielded *p*-fuchsin, and this method was used on a manufacturing scale by Monnet and Dury in Lyons. A fair yield of *p*-fuchsin hydroiodide was also obtained by simply heating iodoform with pure aniline. Dyes of the aurin type have been recently obtained by H. Baines and J. E. Driver by heating dry sodium and potassium salts of phenol and cresols in the vapour of chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1214; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 907, 910.)

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to determine whether compounds of the type of benzeins can be obtained by the condensation of chloroform, carbontetrachloride and iodoform with resorcin and other hydroxy aromatic compounds.

Excess of pure and dry chloroform or carbontetrachloride was dropped through a long reflux condenser into molten resorcin or other hydroxy compound at a temperature of 140° to 160°C . Powdered anhydrous zinc chloride was then added to the mass and the mixture was heated to a temp. of 180° to 200°C for 3 to 4 hours when the reaction was complete. The product when purified and analysed was found to be a benzein.

In the case of condensation with chloroform the leuco condensation-product is apparently oxidised by air to the carbinol stage.

The condensations of iodoform with resorcin and other hydroxy aromatic compounds have been effected by heating a mixture of the components in requisite proportions at 160° to 180°C ., with or without the addition of anhydrous zinc chloride.

Identical product, *viz.*, resorcin-*o-p*-dihydroxy-benzein, has also been prepared by Sen and Sarkar by condensing *o-p*-dihydroxy benzyl alcohol with resorcin in the presence of conc. sulphuric acid of sp. gr. 1.84. (To be shortly published.) The products of the condensation of pyrogallol with chloroform and iodoform are identical and non-fluorescent. The condensation product of hydroquinone and iodoform exhibits weak blue fluorescence in alkaline solution but in dilute alcoholic solution it shows a marked green fluorescence.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(1). *Chloroform and Resorcin.*—5 gms. of dried resorcin were melted in a wide-mouthed flask provided with a long reflux condenser. 5 to 6 c.c. of extra pure chloroform were added drop by drop to the molten mass in the course of 15 minutes. Immediately reddish brown colour developed. Fused zinc chloride (2 gms.) was added and

the temp. was raised to 180° to 200°C. Hydrochloric acid was evolved (detected by ammonia) and the reaction was complete in 3 to 4 hours. Excess of chloroform was driven off and the product was washed with hot water acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was then dissolved in dil. sodium hydroxide solution and the alkaline solution was filtered. From the filtrate the original compound was precipitated by dil. hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with hot water containing hydrochloric acid and finally purified from rectified spirit when an orange yellow micro-crystalline powder was obtained. Yield 4 gms. It does not melt below 290°C. It dissolves in alkali with red colour and green fluorescence. It is soluble in alcohol and acetone (green fluorescence), but insoluble in benzene and ether. It dyes wool and silk an orange shade. (Found: C=71·10% and H=3·79%; Resorcin-*o-p*-dihydroxy-benzene, $C_{12}H_{10}O_2$ requires C=71·25% and H=3·75%). On bromination it gave a tetra-bromo compound like eosin which dyes wool and silk a red shade. (Found: Br=50·11%. Tetra-bromo resorcin-*o-p*-dihydroxy-benzene, $C_{12}H_6O_2Br_4$ requires Br=50·3%).

(2) *Chloroform and Pyrogallol*.—3·75 gms. of pyrogallol and 4 c.c. of chloroform were heated with 2 gms. of fused zinc chloride as in expt. (1), for 3 to 4 hours. Similar method of purification was adopted as in expt. (1). A black product was obtained which does not melt below 250°C. It dissolves in alkali without any fluorescence. It is soluble in alcohol, sparingly so in acetone, but insoluble in benzene and ether. (Found: C=61·82% and H=3·38%. Pyrogallol-*o-m-p*-trihydroxy benzene, $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C=61·95% and H=3·26%).

(3) *Iodoform and Resorcinol*.—3·5 gms. of resorcin and 4 gms. of iodoform were intimately mixed together and the mixture was heated at a temp. of 160°-180°C

for 3 to 4 hours. Processes of purification as in expt. (1). (Found: C=71.04% and H=3.85%. Resorcin-*o-p*-dihydroxy benzein, $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C=71.25% and H=3.75%.)

(4) *Iodoform and Pyrogallol*.—3.75 gms. of pyrogallol and 3.9 gms. iodoform were mixed together and the mixture was heated to a temp. of 160° to 180°C. It was purified as before. (Found: C=61.75% and H=3.46%. Pyrogallol-*o-m-p*-trihydroxy benzein, $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C=61.95% and H=3.26%.)

(5) *Iodoform and Hydroquinone*.—3.5 gms. of hydroquinone and 3.9 gms. of iodoform were treated exactly in the same way in which iodoform and resorcin were treated. The purification of the condensation product was exactly similar as in previous experiments. Hydroquinone-*o-m'*-dihydroxy benzein thus obtained does not melt below 250°C. It dissolves in alkali with red colour and faint blue fluorescence. It is very soluble in alcohol and acetone (green fluorescence) but insoluble in ether and benzene. (Found: C=70.95% and H=3.9%. Hydroquinone-*o-m'*-dihydroxy benzein, $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C=71.25% and H=3.75%.)

(6) *Carbontetrachloride and Resorcinol*.—5 gms. of resorcin were treated with 6 to 7 c.c. of carbontetrachloride precisely in the same manner as in expt. (1). The condensation product has identical properties as of the product obtained in expt. (1). (Found: C=71.1% and H=3.64%. Resorcin-*o-p*-dihydroxy benzein, $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C=71.25% and H=3.75%.)

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